

CNN-Based Soil-Seed Recommender

Vyshnavi Babu S
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
vyshnavibabus2023b@mca.ajce.in

Anit James
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
anitjames@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— India is the land of agriculture and is among the top three global producers of many seeds. The Indian farmer lies at the heart of the agricultural sector yet most Indian farmers remain at the bottom of the social strata. In addition, farmers find it difficult to decide which seed is best suitable and profitable for their soil, in spite of the few technological solutions that exist today, due to the variation in soil types across geographical regions. This paper proposes a seed recommendation system that uses a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), MobileNetV2 Architecture to predict the optimal seed to be grown by analyzing various parameters.

Keywords- Image classification, Deep learning, Convolutional Neural Network, MobileNetV2 Architecture

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture has historically been and remains to this day one of the main pillars of the Indian economy as two-thirds of the Indian population is directly dependent on agriculture for their livelihood. An equally vital fact is that it contributes to 20% of India's Global Domestic Product (GDP). At the crux of the agriculture sector lies the farmer, the Annadatta (Food Provider) of our country, who is facing many adversities today:

- 1) With the multiplicity in soil types across the country farmers usually find it difficult to decide which seed is best suitable and profitable to their soil, their conditions, their region, and hence end up facing many losses.
- 2) Presently it is extremely difficult for farmers to predict the yield for a particular sowing season and the profit that they can earn due to unpredictable weather conditions.
- 3) Dismally low profits that farmers earn for their produce because of the 'farm to market' mechanism which involves hundreds of middlemen who eat up most of the profits by transporting and selling seeds.

Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence find many applications in the modern agriculture industry. Techniques such as precision agriculture and seed recommender systems can be used to improve overall harvest quality, yield prediction, pest detection in plants and poor nutrition of farms. Deployment of AI systems can provide a shot in the arm to the beleaguered agricultural sector.

India's current agricultural woes cast serious doubt on the future of the sector. The agricultural sector contributes 20% of GDP by hiring almost two-thirds of the workforce. Nearly 85% of Indian farmers operate with less than 5 acres of land, undertake significant product and market risks every season and are forced to rely on non-institutional credit sources due to a lack of collateral. Farmers with small holdings also account for 46% of cultivated land, half of the agricultural production, and a much higher share of high-value seeds. But they are routinely excluded from modern market arrangements such as contract farming and direct purchases due to low literacy rates.

This paper describes a soil analysis and seed prediction mechanism that uses a Convolutional Neural Network, MobileNetV2 Architecture to solve some of the long-standing problems of the Indian agricultural sector and increase profitability for the average farmer. Additionally, it details the design and implementation of a website that serves as a marketplace for farmers and potential seed buyers, hence eliminating the need for a middleman. The remainder of the paper is divided into 3 sections as follows:

- 1) Section 2 details past work done in Seed Prediction and Soil Classification.
- 2) Section 3 describes the flow of the proposed system and its implementation.
- 3) Section 4 mentions the conclusion.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

In this section, we review, summarize and analyze work related to Seed Prediction and Soil Classification in agriculture.

Babu et al. [1] described a model that applies Precision Agriculture (PA) principles to small, open farms at the individual farmer and seed level, to affect a grade of control over variability. The goal of the model was to recommend seeds to even the smallest farmer at the level of his/her smallest plot of the crop,

using the most accessible technologies such as SMS and email. The model was designed for the state of Kerala.

Pudumalar et al. [2] propose a recommender system on precision agriculture using data mining techniques. Crop recommendation was based on the study data of their soil types, soil characteristics, and crop yield. Their system used an ensemble method using majority voting, consisting of four individual models, namely, CHAID, Random tree, Naive Bayes, and K-Nearest Neighbors.

Rajak et al. [3] proposed an ensemble model with a majority voting technique, where the ensemble model comprises four individual models, namely, Support Vector Machine, Artificial Neural Network, Random Tree, and Naive Bayes. Their dataset included various traits of soil like pH, water density, etc. as features collected from soil testing labs and universities.

Reddy et al. [4] proposed a two-step model - the first step for soil classification and a second step for crop suggestion. The first step used chemical structures of soil such as moisture, the content of potassium, magnesium, etc. to predict the soil series or the soil type. The second step used features such as the soil series, temperature, humidity, rainfall, and pH. Classification algorithms like Support Vector Machine, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Bagging were utilized to suggest seeds. Although this paper did not implement the system proposed by them, its' two-step model inspired us to use different machine learning algorithms to achieve different goals of the system by using a two-step model.

Savla et al. [5] compared classification algorithms and their performance in yield prediction in precision agriculture. These algorithms were realized on a data set collected for several years in yield prediction on the soya bean crop. The algorithms used were Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, Neural Network, Bagging, and Bayes. The authors concluded that bagging was the best algorithm for yield prediction as the error deviation was minimum.

Manjula et al. [6] developed a framework called extensible Seed Yield Prediction Framework (XCYPF) that enabled the flexible inclusion of numerous techniques towards seed yield prediction. They also developed a tool that would help people to predict crop yield for various crops with dependent and independent variables.

Kumar et al. [7] proposed a Crop Selection Method (CSM) to solve the seed selection problem and improve the net yield rate of the crop. The method suggested a series of crop to be selected over a season as factors like weather, soil type, water density, and crop type.

The predicted value of influential parameters determined the accuracy of the model. They also illustrated the significance of crop selection and the factors affecting seed selection like production rate, market price, and government policies.

Ahamed et al. [8] used data mining techniques to estimate the crop yield for cereal crops in major districts of Bangladesh. They future a system that consisted of two parts: Clustering (for creating district clusters) and Classification using, KNN (k-nearest neighbor), Linear Regression, (ANN) artificial neural network in rapid miner tool. Their data set included 5 environmental variables, 3 biotic variables, and 2 area-related variables to determine the crop yield in different districts.

The systems proposed by the above papers have a few drawbacks:

1) References [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6] and [7] require site-specific features like chemical properties of the soil, such as the content of minerals, pH, etc. and other properties such as wind speed which may be tough and/or expensive for farmers to collect.

III. METHODOLOGY

A user clicks a picture of soil and feeds these inputs to the system. The output will be a list of seed recommendations best for the soil image fed.

A. System Overview

Soil Classification using MobileNetV2 Architecture:

We process the image of the soil that is fed into the system by the user and classify it into one of the four classes of soil, namely Red, Alluvial, Black, and Clay. This is done by a Convolutional Neural Network, MobileNetV2 Architecture whose implementation details are discussed in the following subsections. After the soil type is predicted, a few seeds are shortlisted that are suitable to be cultivated in that soil type. Hence, this step ensures that the quality of the seeds recommended is good, as only seeds suitable to the soil type are shortlisted.

B. System Architecture

1) Mobile Net / Convolutional Neural Network:

Fig. 1. System Architecture

i). Dataset Collection and Data Pre-Processing:

The dataset used in training the parameters of this algorithm includes images of the diverse soil sorts namely, Red Soil, Black Soil, Clay Soil, and Alluvial Soil. The dataset includes 150-200 images of each soil type in the training set and about 50 images in the test set that is 80% train data and 20% test data. This data is collected from the Soil Classification Image Dataset on Kaggle and from similar other online sources.

The images in the dataset are of various sizes and dimensions, and hence need to be resized and pre-processed before they are fed into the model. The algorithm needs to recite a colored image for our use case, and every colored image in RGB format has three networks, one for each color, Red, Green, and Blue. Hence, the images are first resized to 300x300x3 images. The images are then converted into numerical (pixel intensities) arrays so that the model can process the data. This numerical data is then fed into the Machine Learning model.

The machine learning model used to classify these images into the different soil types is a Convolutional Neural Network, MobileNetV2 Architecture. Mobile Net uses a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture model to categorize images. It is open- sourced by Google. Currently, it has two stable versions:

1. MobilenetV1
2. MobileNetV2

MobilenetV2 is a refined version of MobilenetV1. This makes it even more effective and powerful. The MobileNetV2 models are faster due to the reduced

model size and complexity. This is a pre-trained model for image classification. Pre-trained models are deep neural networks that are trained using a large images dataset. Using the pre-trained models, we need not build

or train the neural network from scratch, thereby saving time for development.

Fig. 2. The image above shows the architecture and the number of layers of a pre-trained MobileNetV2 model.

The network architecture of the same is discussed below:

Type / Stride	Filter Shape	Input Size
Conv / s2	$3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 32$	$224 \times 224 \times 3$
Conv dw / s1	$3 \times 3 \times 32$ dw	$112 \times 112 \times 32$
Conv / s1	$1 \times 1 \times 32 \times 64$	$112 \times 112 \times 32$
Conv dw / s2	$3 \times 3 \times 64$ dw	$112 \times 112 \times 64$
Conv / s1	$1 \times 1 \times 64 \times 128$	$56 \times 56 \times 64$
Conv dw / s1	$3 \times 3 \times 128$ dw	$56 \times 56 \times 128$
Conv / s1	$1 \times 1 \times 128 \times 128$	$56 \times 56 \times 128$
Conv dw / s2	$3 \times 3 \times 128$ dw	$56 \times 56 \times 128$
Conv / s1	$1 \times 1 \times 128 \times 256$	$28 \times 28 \times 128$
Conv dw / s1	$3 \times 3 \times 256$ dw	$28 \times 28 \times 256$
Conv / s1	$1 \times 1 \times 256 \times 256$	$28 \times 28 \times 256$
Conv dw / s2	$3 \times 3 \times 256$ dw	$28 \times 28 \times 256$
Conv / s1	$1 \times 1 \times 256 \times 512$	$14 \times 14 \times 256$
5x Conv dw / s1	$3 \times 3 \times 512$ dw	$14 \times 14 \times 512$
Conv / s1	$1 \times 1 \times 512 \times 512$	$14 \times 14 \times 512$
Conv dw / s2	$3 \times 3 \times 512$ dw	$14 \times 14 \times 512$
Conv / s1	$1 \times 1 \times 512 \times 1024$	$7 \times 7 \times 512$
Conv dw / s2	$3 \times 3 \times 1024$ dw	$7 \times 7 \times 1024$
Conv / s1	$1 \times 1 \times 1024 \times 1024$	$7 \times 7 \times 1024$
Avg Pool / s1	Pool 7×7	$7 \times 7 \times 1024$
FC / s1	1024×1000	$1 \times 1 \times 1024$
Softmax / s1	Classifier	$1 \times 1 \times 1000$

The network consists of 28 convolutional layers and 1 fully connected layer followed by a SoftMax layer. It is noted that batch normalization and ReLU is applied after convolution

Width Multiplier

A width multiplier alpha α is introduced to further reduce computational cost. So M becomes αM . So depth wise separable computational cost becomes

$$D_K \cdot D_K \cdot \alpha M \cdot D_F \cdot D_F + \alpha M \cdot \alpha N \cdot D_F \cdot D_F$$

computational cost with width multiplier where α is between 0 to 1. Typically values of α are 1,0.75,0.5 and 0.25. When $\alpha = 1$ we have a baseline Mobile Net.

Table 6. MobileNet Width Multiplier

Width Multiplier	ImageNet Accuracy	Million Mult-Adds	Million Parameters
1.0 MobileNet-224	70.6%	569	4.2
0.75 MobileNet-224	68.4%	325	2.6
0.5 MobileNet-224	63.7%	149	1.3
0.25 MobileNet-224	50.6%	41	0.5

performance with different α values

Resolution Multiplier

Resolution Multiplier ρ is introduced to control the image resolution of the network. With ρ computational cost becomes

$$D_K \cdot D_K \cdot \alpha M \cdot \rho D_F \cdot \rho D_F + \alpha M \cdot \alpha N \cdot \rho D_F \cdot \rho D_F$$

computational cost with resolution multiplier where ρ is between 0 to 1. The corresponding resolutions are 224, 192, 160, and 128. When $\rho=1$, it is the baseline Mobile Net

Table 7. MobileNet Resolution

Resolution	ImageNet Accuracy	Million Mult-Adds	Million Parameters
1.0 MobileNet-224	70.6%	569	4.2
1.0 MobileNet-192	69.1%	418	4.2
1.0 MobileNet-160	67.2%	290	4.2
1.0 MobileNet-128	64.4%	186	4.2

C. Web Portal

To assimilate all the components of the system we have discussed so far, we decide to create a prototype of a web portal that would use the Seed Recommendation System proposed by this paper. This portal has a very attractive, and user-friendly, user interface. This web portal can be used by any types of users, sellers etc. Farmers can feed in the inputs and get seed recommendations based on those input.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we proposed a web page for the ease of farmers to check the soil image and the recommended seed for it using the Flask web framework connecting our proposed model in the backend. The user is asked to upload the soil image of theirs. The values are passed into a machine learning model-MobileNetV2 Architecture. From the above input values the exact soil prediction is made and the result is displayed in the prediction page. The proposed system has improved accuracy than the existing system. The proposed system achieved the training accuracy of 97.34% and the validation accuracy of 99.21% which is better than the existing system model. MobileNetV2 has been pre-trained on large datasets, making it possible to use transfer learning to train new models on smaller datasets, which can be more cost-effective and time-efficient compared to training a traditional CNN from scratch. Overall, the proposed system model has been designed to address some of the challenges associated with deploying existing system models. By focusing on efficiency and accuracy, MobileNetV2 provides a powerful and flexible tool for computer vision applications.

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